

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol.XVI.Book.I-IV

January - December 2024

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series

Vol.XVI. Book. I-IV

January-December

2024

Sanskrit Research Foundation

T.C 39/37

Thiruvananthapuram-36

KIRANĀVALĪ

ISSN 0975-4067

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14576256>

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

A Peer-Reviewed Research Journal

Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

Executive Editor

Prof. Dr.C.S.Sasikumar (Rtd.)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

drsasikumarc@gmail.com

Managing Editor

Prof. Dr.G.Narayanan

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

Editorial board

Dr.V.Sisupalapanikkar, Professor of Sanskrit(Rtd.) Uty. of Kerala

Dr.K.Muthulakshmi, Professor of Vedanta, S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.R.Vijayakumar, Professor of Vyakarana(Rtd.), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.P.Chithambaran, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd),S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.P.K.Dharmarajan, Professor of Sahitya, (Rtd) S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.K.K.Sundaresan, Associate Professor in Vedanta, SSUS.Kalady

Dr.S.Sobhana, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.T.Devarajan, Professor of Sanskrit (Rtd), University of Kerala

Associate Editor

Dr.R.Jinu

Associate Professor, Dept of English,

Noorul Islam Centre For Higher Education, Kumaracoil,

Thuckalay, Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu

jichelnu@gmail.com

Contents

Editors Note	5
Fractions or kalāsavarṇa - Concepts in the Gaṇitasārasaṅgraha (G.S.S) of Mahāvira	Dr. P.M.Mini 7
Vrikshayurveda Literature- A Review	Dr. K.Murali 12
Existence Of Mind and its Function: Śrī Śankara's Perspective	Dr. V Vasanthakumari 23
Regional Peculiarities in Prakriyāsarvasva	Dr. Yamuna.K 30
Parāstotra - Edition and Study	Dr. J.P. Prajith 37
Alienation through Exile: A Critical Introspection into John Dos Passos' Nineteen Nineteen	Dr. Sanil T. Sunny 44
The Evolution of Indian Sculptural Art: Interaction with Western Styles and Development of Modernism	Dr. T.G Jyothilal 49
Scope of Sanskrit Studies in the Kerala Context	Dr. Shylaja S 55
Desamangalam Srikantha Variar - A Versatile Scholar	Dr.V.P.Udayakumar 67
A Comprehensive Review of Adharaneeya and Dharaneeya Vega	Dr. H.A.Anu, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Haroon Irshad, Dr. Leena P.Nair 72
A Significant Emphasis on Charakokta Chaturvidha Pariksha	Dr.Kesavan.V G, Dr.Haroon Irshad, Dr.Leena P.Nair, Dr. Haritha Chandran 84
Concept Of Manas- A Glimpse from Yoga Darsana	Dr. Anu Gopal, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Leena P Nair, Dr. Haroon Irshad 96
Women Life in Royal Harem- A Study Based on Nāṭyaśāstra And Mālavikāgnimitra	Dr. Ajitha T S 106
Effective Strategies For Implementing The Integrated Teacher Education Programme Under NEP- 2020	Prof. K.K. Harshkumar, Dr. Anand Rautmale 113
“Pancha Mahabhuta in Ayurveda: Understanding and Practical Applications”	Dr. Aswiny Sreekumar.T 121
“Dynamic Portrayals of Women in Amarushatak: Unravelling Love, Creation, Destruction, Submission, and Dominance”	Dr. Preeti R. Pujara 135
Literary Representation of the Ashtamudi Lake sketched through Poetic Imagery: An Exploration based on Selected Poems in Malayalam	Jayalekshmi J 145
Reviving Classical Narratives: Exploring the Cultural, Linguistic, and Literary Significance of Sanskrit Literature in Contemporary Contexts	Dr. Yeshpal, 155
Vedic Thought on Nakshatra Science	Dr. Kanta 172
Vedāntic Reflections in Kālidāsa's Literature: A Journey through Ancient Wisdom	Dr. K. K. Abdul Majeed 179
The Transformative Power of Yogic Meditation: Insights from the Isha Upanishad	Dev Prakash Gujela, Neha Gujela 188
Sanskrit: The Language of Innovation in Ancient Indian Knowledge Systems.	Dr. Abdul Rasheed K. 197
The Role of Vedānta as a Mediator between Science and Religion	Dr. Abdulla Sha R., Dr. Midhun P., 207

Concept of Guṇa in Bhagavad Gīta	Dr. Shyji K.K.	212
Pancatantram's perspective of accepting an 'hors de combat'	Kasthuri P. K.	217
Integral Yoga of Sri Aurobindo	Remya.S	223
The Historical Aspects Of 'Translation' (Anuvādam) - An Overview	Dr. Sajeesh C S	227
The Malayali Diaspora in the US: A close reading of Mira Jacob	Nirupama Suneetha	235
From Elancon To Kollam: The Transformation of A Port City	Gowri S Panicker	242
Influence of Nārayaṇīya on Kṛṣṇagīti	Dr Jayanisha K	255
Subverting Ableist Binaries: An Analysis of the Confluence of Disability Studies and Blue Humanities in Toni Crowther's From Wheelchair to Water	Sneha Jacob	263
Connecting the Concept of 'Avatar' to the Concept of Consciousness in Upanishads	Venugopalan P.M	269
Extraction of historicity from Sanskrit literature	Soorya A.P	281
चिन्सुखेन प्रतिपादितं अविद्यालक्षणम्	डॉ. सन्तोष सि. आर्	285
सामाजिकसमस्यापरिहारे भरतीयज्ञानपरम्परान्तर्गतस्य योगशास्त्रस्य स्थानम्	डा. श्रीजित् टि.जि	289
पतञ्जलिकालीनः लोकव्यवहारः-महाभाष्याधारेण एकमनुशीलनम्	डा.रूपा. वि	293
मानवीयमूल्यबोधोत्तरणे मूच्छकटिकम्	ड.मृत्युञ्जयमण्डलः परेशकैवर्त्यः	299
रघुवंशमहाकाव्ये रसतत्त्वसमीक्षणम्	काञ्चनवारिकः	304
नारीचैतन्योद्बोधे शङ्खनादः	डॉ टुम्पा जाना	308
आधुनिकसंस्कृतसाहित्ये गलज्जलिकायाः वैशिष्ट्यम्	सतीश चन्द्र दास	313
श्रीमच्छंकराचार्यकृतच्छान्दोग्योपनिषद्भाष्यस्य कतिपयशब्दवाक्यानां रूपवाक्यशब्दार्थतत्त्वनिरूपणम्	रणिता घोष	321
सदाचारो वेदाश्च ।	डा.अशोक कुमार एन्.के.	327
साम्प्रतिकसन्दर्भे अपरिग्रहः	डॉ. शुभमयपाहाडी	331
मनुसंहिता : 'ब्रह्मतत्त्व' विषयकम् एकं संक्षिप्तं मतम्	अमल कुमार कर	335
श्रीकाशीमठाधीशानां श्रीमत्सुधीन्द्रतीर्थानां स्तोत्रेषु छन्दांसि तथा सौन्दर्यम्	दिव्यश्री जगदीश पै बि. , & भास्कर वि भट्टः	339
सिद्धान्तग्रन्थेषु ब्राह्ममाणम्	डा. राघवेंद्रः	347
एतत्संज्ञेत्यत्र कः समासः	डा. गोपालकृष्णन् रघुः	352
मेघदूतस्य सांस्कृतिकमीमांसा	डा. सत्येन्दु शर्मा	356
जान्-म्यूर-प्रणीतस्य 'श्रीपौलचरित्रम्' इति महाकाव्यस्य संस्कृतालङ्कारशास्त्रदृष्ट्या समीक्षामिका विमृष्टिः	डा. सौम्यजित् सेनः	360
आधुनिकयुगे संस्कृतशिक्षा प्रसारार्थं विद्यासागरस्यावदानम्	डः तानिया-सिकदारः	369
तद्धितप्रत्ययेषु इत्संज्ञकवर्णाः ।	आतिरा. जि	372
अद्वैतसिद्धेः मङ्गलश्लोकस्य अप्रामाण्यशङ्कावारणम्	कार्तिक शर्मा के , ड. हरिकृष्ण शर्मा के.एन्	376
न्यायव्याकरणतन्त्रानुरोधे पदस्वरूपविवेचनम्	प्रणबेष् भट्टाचार्यः	381
पीयूषवर्षश्रीजयदेवाचार्य-श्रीकेशवमिश्रयोः मते शान्तरसविमर्शः	सत्येनशीटः	387
आलंकारिकदण्डिस्वीकृतः शब्दालङ्कारप्रपञ्चः	डॉ. शुभ्रजित् सेनः	393
लिधा एव पदशब्दस्य प्रवृत्तिः	डा. सुदीप-मण्डलः	400
About the journal		407

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14684543>

Connecting the Concept of 'Avatar' to the Concept of Consciousness in Upanishads

Venugopalan P.M¹

Abstract

The profound philosophy of the Vedas and Upanishads is presented in the form of stories in the Puranas. Avatars appear in the Puranas. The question arises: the purpose of puranas being the exposition of the Vedas and Upanishads, why there are contradictions in the stories of Avatars. In an attempt to understand this problem, this paper analyses the concept of 'Avatar', with reference to some incarnations of Lord Vishnu. Viewing it from a different period can often lead to contradictions and controversies. This paper also discusses the relevance of this topic in the present times.

Key words: *Avatar*, Puranas, *Upanishads*, *Saguna Brahman*, *Bhakti Yoga*

Introduction

Vedanta, which is one of the six orthodox schools of Indian philosophy, considers *Brahman* as Sat, Cit, Ananda². It is mentioned in Aitareya Upanishad 3.1.3 that *Brahman* is the universal consciousness and everything in this universe is a manifestation of *Brahman* (Gambhirananda). *Atman* is the individual consciousness. According to Taittiriya Upanishad 2.1.1, *Brahman/Atman* is all pervasive and eternal (Chinmayananda). The nature of Brahman, or Atman, is Existence-Knowledge-Bliss (yogananda.com.au/upa/Upanishads03.html). Jivatma³ has limited himself

-
1. Research Scholar, Department of Yoga and Spirituality, Swami Vivekananda Yoga, Anusandhana, Samsthana (S- VYASA), Bangalore, India – 560019
 2. Sat, Cit, Ananda means Pure Existence, Pure Awareness, and Pure Bliss.
 3. Jivatma is the individual self, which resides in all beings assuming a suitable form conforming to the vasana (A past impression in the mind that influences behaviour), it has accumulated during the previous janmas (births).

through *avidya*⁴, which prevents it from realising its true nature. As a result, we entertain the illusion of our body as well as everything in the outside world as real. The erroneous identification of the body (combination of five senses and the master sense, mind) with the *Atman* due to ignorance is the root cause of human sufferings and miseries and for births and deaths (sivanandaonline.org/Brahma Sutras). According to Sankara Bashya of Chandogya Upanishad 8.3-4, the goal of life of *Jiva* is to become one with the *Atman/Brahman*, which is called Self-Realization (Moksha) (Klostermaier). The human mind is accustomed to words, images, and symbols. Hence it is difficult for a layman to meditate on Nirguna Brahman⁵, which is considered as the meditation of the highest order, which leads to *sadyomukti* (immediate liberation) (sivanandaonline.org/Brahma Sutras). Vedas and Upanishads have introduced the concept of Saguna Brahman⁶ to help those people to move along the path of devotion (Bhakti) and attain *moksha* (freedom/liberation). *Bhagavad Gita*, an authentic text on *Bhakti Yoga*, states in 18.66 that single-minded devotion to God is the surest path to *moksha* (Ranganadanandaswamikal). The *Bhakti Yoga* has its origin in the Upanishads. *Śvetāśvatara Upanishad* (6.23) states, “*yasya deve parā bhaktir yathā deve tathā gurau tasyaite kathitā hy arthāḥ prakāśante mahātmanah*” (“He who has supreme devotion to the Deity, and as much of it to the guru as to the Deity, to him indeed, to the great-souled one, these subject matters that have been spoken become revealed”) (S. Gambhirananda). In *Bhagavad Gita* 18.66, it is stated that the path of *Bhakti Yoga* is considered the most suitable path for moksha to those people who are unable to tread the path of *Jnana Yoga* (Ranganadanandaswamikal). That is why the Bhakti cult developed by Sri Ramanuja, interpreting Bhakti based on the Saguna Brahman philosophy of Vedas gained popularity (Wrenn). According to Bhakti Yoga, gradually, as the *Bhakta* advances in his worship of the Lord, his purified mind gets dissolved in Consciousness and

4 Any knowledge, which leads one to more attachment thus getting him trapped in the vicious cycle of births and deaths is considered as inferior knowledge or *avidya*.

5 Brahman without attributes, which is beyond the perception of the mind and senses

6 Brahman with infinite attributes, including form.

he is freed from the *samsaric*⁷ wheel of births and deaths (Burgin).

The Puranas, which fall in to the 'smṛiti' category of the ancient scriptures, considered to be written between 3-10 AD, centuries after the Vedas were written, by different personalities in the Vyasa lineage, serve as a complement to the Vedas by helping to understand the philosophy of the Vedas and conveying the ethos of the vedic culture through the innumerable stories narrated in them, which are highly symbolic in nature. "Puranas are fluid bodies of literature that continue to be transformed through the centuries by the process of transmission and adaptation" (Bryant).

According to the Puranas, the triple gods of Hinduism, *Brahma*, *Vishnu*, and *Siva*, called *Trimurti* (Triple Deities), are considered manifestations of the same Supreme Īśvara (*Saguṇa Brahman*).

Concept of *Avatar* (incarnation)

Concept of *Avatar* is a unique idea, which is an extension of the *Saguṇa Brahman* concept in Bhakti Yoga philosophy. Sanskrit meaning of *Avatar* is 'appearance', 'manifestation', 'descent', or 'materialization'. Rudimentary idea of *Avatar* can be found in the Kena Upanishad, which narrates the manifestation of Brahman as 'Yaksha' to destroy the vanity of Indra, Agni, and Vayu⁸ (S. Gambhirananda, Kena Upanishad). The Puranas, introduced the concept of *Avatar* through stories. Bhagavad Gita states, "Though unborn, the imperishable Self, and also the Lord of all beings, brooding over nature, which is Mine own, yet I am born through My own power. Whenever there is decay of righteousness, then I Myself come forth for the protection of the good, for the destruction of evildoers, for the sake of firmly establishing righteousness, I am born from age to age" (Bhagavad Gita IV-6, 7, 8).

The concept of *Avatar* is identical to the *Ishvara* (God) concept. The difference is that *Ishvara* is considered as Eternal and Absolute, while *Avatars* assume particular forms and are here for a limited period of time to accomplish specific duties (Sai).

7 "samsaric" means the indefinitely repeated cycles of birth, suffering, and death caused by karma.

8 In Kena Upanishads the entire 3rd Chapter from sloka 1 to 12 shows how Brahman appearing in the form of 'Yaksha' destroyed the egoism of Gods Indra, Agni, and Vayu.

Philosophy behind the concept of *Avatar*

- Swami Sivananda describes *Avatar* as the descent of God on earth for the spiritual upliftment of man by developing Bhakti in him and enabling him to perform duty without desire for reward. *Avatar* removes the veil of ignorance of thousands of men and women and takes them to Moksha (Sivanandaonline.org.Doctrine of Avtarhood). Sankaracharya in his commentary on Brahma Sutra (III, 2, 14) states “Those other passages (in the Vedas and puranas), on the other hand, which refer to a Brahman qualified by form do not aim at setting forth the nature of Brahman, but rather at enjoining the worship of Brahman.” Lord Krishna has clearly stated in Bhagavad Gita that the concept of Saguna Brahman and Avatar is not meant for Jnana yogis (Bhagavad Gita VII-24)⁹. Bhagavad Gita 12.8 declares, those who completely fix their mind on Lord Krishna and surrender their *Buddhi* to Lord Krishna remain in him (Ranganadanandaswamikal) and are liberated by going beyond the vicious cycle of birth and death. On reflection, anybody can feel that the stories of the incarnations must have given solace to the people, whose life became miserable due to the atrocities perpetrated by evildoers like powerful demons helping them to come out of the utter confusion and despair by instilling confidence in them that God will protect them in all difficulties. These stories are more powerful than stores, which convey only moral lessons because they help in developing *bhakti* towards God in devotees and prompt them to surrender completely to God. This will gradually purify their minds and lead them to *moksha*. Purification of mind, which brings the mind to complete stillness, is a prerequisite for *moksha* (Madhavananda). Mandukya Upanishad 3.46 states that purity of mind brings mind to complete stillness. Motionless mind becomes identified with *Brahman* (S. Gambhirananda, Mandukya Upanisad).
 - Going by the Upanishads assertion that the Individual Self (Atman) and the Universal Self (Brahman) are one and the
-
- 9 “Those devoid of reason think of Me, the unmanifest, as having manifestation, knowing not My supreme nature, imperishable, most excellent. “ (Bhagavad Gita VII-24)

same, all living beings are incarnations of God only. But due to the bondage caused by ignorance, the Jivatma does not realize its real nature and cannot exercise his full divine powers. Whereas the incarnation of God

- knows fully well its true nature and hence can manifest all his divine powers to the full extent in order to accomplish the purpose of his descent (Bhagavad Gita IV-6) (Jayaram).
- By presenting 'fish', 'tortoise', and the 'boar' as the *Avatars* of Vishnu, these subhuman creatures are elevated to the status of the Almighty, which conveys the *Upanishadic* idea of unity of all beings and the need to show empathy to every living being.

Concept of Avatar vis-à-vis. other Religions and different Indian schools of thought

The doctrine of the Incarnation is a fundamental characteristic of Christianity, which is a widely accepted belief in the European world. The Hindu concept of *avatar* differ significantly with the Christian concept of Incarnation. In Christianity, God Incarnated only once as Jesus of Nazareth (Samples), whereas an avatar in Hinduism is neither a messenger of God nor a prophet but God himself, who descent on earth in a mortal body in various forms as humans and animals (Jayaram. The Meaning and Concept of Incarnation in Hinduism)

The purpose of the Incarnation in Christianity was to reveal God to mankind and to redeem sinful human beings through Christ's sacrificial atonement (Titus 2:13) (Samples). "The Son of God became a man to enable men to become sons of God" (Lewis, 1952)¹⁰, (Samples) whereas the in Brihadaranyaka Upanishad Volume II.4.4.6, it is stated that the purpose of incarnation in Hindu religion is to enable men to transcend bad as well as good deeds and performing deeds without desires, and become one with Brahman (Yati). Jesus was considered to be a historical figure who took birth, lived in this world, and died 2,000 years ago (Valea). But the avatars of Hinduism cannot be attributed any specific historical dates as these are characters of symbolic stories narrated in the Puranas to convey the messages of the Vedas and Upanishads.

10 In this quote, Lewis slightly rephrases a statement made by the ancient church father Athanasius (ca. 296– 373).

Islam totally rejects the idea of incarnation of God into human form. “Worship Allah (alone), avoid all deities (An-Nahl16:36) (legacy.quran.com/16/36). However, Islam recognizes the concept of prophethood. According to Islam, the Prophets and Messengers were distinguished human beings with the purest and highest mental and spiritual qualities, who conduct all the routine natural activities and undergo natural experiences just like other human beings; who were specially selected to receive the revelation from Allah. The purpose of the messengers and prophets is to guide people through the right method of worship of Allah by conveying the revelations received by them from Allah. Prophet Muhammad is considered as the Last and Final Messenger of Allah (en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Prophets_and_messengers_in_Islam).

Out of the six Orthodox schools (*Astika*) of Indian philosophy, Samkhya and Poorva Mimamsa schools reject the idea of a creator God and hence do not approve of the concept of Avatar (Cohen). Yoga philosophy lays emphasis on Self-realization by getting elevated to superior levels of consciousness. According to yoga philosophy, the belief in God is only required as a help in the initial stage of mental concentration and control of the mind and hence the concept of avatar is nowhere discussed (yogapedia.com/definition/5395/avatar). Nyāya and Vaisheshika, which also accept the authority of the Vedas believe in the existence of *Isvara* (God). But no mention of Avatars is seen anywhere in these scriptures.

Uttara Mimamsa (Vedanta), which is among the six orthodox schools can be classified mainly into three: Absolute Monism of Shankara, Vishishta Advaita or qualified monism of Ramanuja, and Dvaita of Madhvah (George). There are other classifications also. *Advaita Vedanta*, states, “*brahma satyam jaganmithya jivo brahmaiva napaṛāh*”, which means that *Brahman* is the only reality, the world is unreal, and there is no difference between *Brahman* and Atman. Mandukya Upanishad 2.1 proclaims, “*Ayam atma brahma*,” (“This Atman (Self) is Brahman”). To explain Saguna Brahman concept including *Avatar*, which is an integral part of the *Saguna Brahman* concept, Sankaracharya introduced the concept of *Maya*, which is explained as that which is superimposed on Brahman (shankaracharya.org/advaita_vedanta.php/The Advaita Philosophy

Of Sri Sankara).

The *Avatar* concept well fits into the Vishishtadvaita philosophy of Ramanuja, which believes in a Personal God or *Isvara* with attributes, who is considered as the creator, sustainer, and destroyer of all existence (Srinivasan). Dvaita Vedanta also accepts the concept of Avatar (hinduism.stackexchange.com/questions/18987/avataravaada-and-vedanta-are-there-any-contradiction?)

The ancient Indian Religions of Buddhism and Jainism, and schools of thoughts of Carvaka and Ajivika, which are considered as the Heterodox Schools of Indian Philosophy (Nastika) are built on the foundation of atheism. Since they rejected the idea of a creator God, these philosophies do not subscribe to the idea of Avatarhood. They considered that the gods play no role in spiritual liberation and enlightenment. Buddhist philosophers even argued that belief in god or gods is a distraction to those who strive for enlightenment (Cohen).

Relevance of Avatar stories in the present-day context

- Story of Avatars being the literary and imaginary extension of the Vedas, righteousness and morality are highlighted as means for attaining purification of mind.
- Rama, in the words of Swami Vivekananda – is “the embodiment of truth, of morality, the ideal son, the ideal husband, and above all, the ideal king.” This idea of Rama is most relevant and worth practicing in modern times of unrest and chaos.
- Mahatma Gandhi and various leaders of Indian Freedom movement as well as famous writers like Henry David Theroux, John Keats and Walter Hagan and world-famous composer Beethoven and various other personalities drew inspiration from Bhagavad Gita. Even today, people from all over the world are finding comfort and guidance in the pages of the Bhagavad Gita.
- The story of *Narasimha Avatar* helps foster the faith of the devotees that they are under the protection of God, whenever they are in trouble. This story clearly passes on to the devotees the knowledge as to how in the modern world of chaos and unrest, *Bhakti Yoga* should be practised to attain peace of mind.

Arguments against the concept of Avatar.

There are some common objections raised against the concept of Avatar. “How can the unborn God assume the form of a living being?

Is it not a contradiction to present the Almighty, who is defined as infinite and eternal in a finite and perishable human body? How can the Purusha who stands as the Witness be presented as involving actively in a finite body?” Swami Sivananda argues that the doctrine of *Avatarahood* is perfectly rational, logical, and tenable. He states, “God is omnipotent and omniscient. God who has created the bodies for others, can create a body for Himself as well. As He has control over Maya, He is fully conscious of His divine nature though He assumes a form. Still, He is infinite and unconditioned” (Sivanandaonline.org.Doctrine of Avtarhood).

Sankaracharya states, “Just as the light of the sun or the moon after having passed through space enters into contact with a finger or some other limiting adjunct, and, according as the latter is straight or bent, itself becomes straight or bent as it were; so Brahman also assumes, as it were, the form of the earth and the other limiting adjuncts with which it enters into connection.” To the question, does this not imply a contradiction of assertions of the Upanishads that Brahman does not possess double characteristics (Bṛ. Up. III, 8, 8; Ka. Up. I, 3, 15), Sankara answers in the following words. “By no means, what is merely due to a limiting adjunct cannot constitute an attribute of a substance, and the limiting adjuncts are, moreover, presented by Nescience only. That the primeval natural Nescience leaves room for all practical life and activity--whether ordinary or based on the Veda (Brahma Sutras (Shankaracharya Bashya) III, 2, 15 (Thibaut).”

Relation between Avatars and Social Ethos

Each *Avatar* glorifies a particular principle and beliefs depending upon the social ethos prevalent at that time. Viewing it from a different period with changed social customs and beliefs, can often lead to contradictions and controversies (Turlapati).

The people living in the present age where human rights and gender equality are considered as indispensable characteristics of a civilized society, cannot digest the act of Rama subjecting Sita to prove her chastity through purification in the fire and his abandoning her afterwards in the forest in the larger interests of fulfilling the duty of a King. Ramayana, which is one of the most popular epics in the world is deeply interwoven into the sociocultural history of

India (Jayaram V). According to the social and cultural customs and beliefs prevalent in that period, these acts of Rama were considered highly admirable, upholding the concept of Dharma.

The wide popularity of Ramayana in many Asian countries including Burma, Indonesia, Cambodia, Laos, Philippines, Sri Lanka, Nepal, Thailand, Malaysia, Japan, Mongolia, Vietnam, and China, shows the social relevance of the characters and the life revolving around them, in these countries because the various elements of the tale find a suitable match with the local cultural ethos of these countries. This story thus can be said to play a considerable role in the cultural unification of these countries in the Asian region (Sharma). Sri Sathya Sai Baba states, "The idea of Rama is most relevant to the world, at a time when it is fraught with chaos and confusion" (Sai Lakshmi).

Symbolism in the story of the Avatars

Different layers of meaning are embedded in the stories of Puranas. Depending upon the degree of intellectual and spiritual advancement, the spiritual aspirant can derive different messages from these stories. While a layman wanders in the periphery of these stories, perceiving only the superficial meaning of these stories resulting in superstitions, perversions of truths, contradictions, and controversies, a person placed in the higher ladders of spirituality, delve deep into these stories and the hidden meanings of these stories unravel themselves as flashes from the depths of consciousness in moments of heightened awareness (Parthasarathy).

The Bhagavad Gita, which is a contribution of the Krishna Avatar is highly symbolic and philosophical. The battle presented here is not a battle in the real sense. It is a symbolic presentation of the battle of good and evil that goes on in our minds. It teaches us how to eradicate 'samskara'¹¹ from our mind, which creates the covering of *avidya* that separates the *Jiva* from *Atman* by following any of the exclusive paths of Jnana Yoga, Raja Yoga, Bhakti Yoga, or Karma Yoga, or various permutations and combinations of these paths, depending on the nature and temperament of the individual and come out of the vicious cycle of birth and death and attain moksha.

According to Sri Sathya Sai, Rāma represents the supreme truth

11 Samskara is the impression created by sensual experiences of all the previous janmas (births) (sunk deep into the subconscious mind(citta))

(Paramatma); Sita represents absolute wisdom (Brahma-jnana), which is thwarted by desire for the golden deer, the result of which was separation (Rama Devi). By understanding the symbolic meaning of Ramayana, the controversies regarding the actions of Rama towards Sita and Vali will disappear into thin air.

Conclusion

Vedas, Upanishads, and Scriptures share real wisdom and declare the purpose of human life as attaining *moksha*. They state that Consciousness is the sub-stratum of everything in this universe and that Consciousness is the eternal reality. Everything else is impermanent. The body as well as the mind is part of matter only; the only difference is that the mind is subtler than the body. Even though it appears that mind is the cause of suffering, and that mind can eradicate suffering, *Upanishads* state that, mind being matter is non-sentient and suffering can be eradicated only when Consciousness shines, which happens when mind gets dissolved completely. To achieve this, many paths are prescribed depending on the mental construct of the *Sadhaka (spiritual aspirant)*. Hinduism allows maximum freedom to the *Sadhaka* in the selection of the path to pursue the goal of self-realization. Depending upon the temperament, taste, and the nature of a person, he can choose any of the exclusive paths prescribed by the *Vedas* or a permutation and combination of different paths. The story of Avatars depicts how the path of *Bhakti Yoga* leads the devotees to Moksha by purifying their minds.

Works Cited

- Bryant, Edwin F. *Krishna, The Beautiful Legend of God*. Penguin Books, 2003.
20 February 2024. <https://www.academia.edu/44305623/Vishnu_Avataras_in_the_Bhagavata_Purana_A_Political_Comment>.
- Burgin, Timothy. www.yogabasics.com/learn/bhakti-yoga-the-yoga-of-devotion/. 30 October 2023. 27 January 2024 . <<https://www.yogabasics.com/learn/bhakti-yoga-the-yoga-of-devotion/>>.
- Chinmayananda, Swami. "Taittiriya Upanishad." Bombay: Central Chinmaya Mission Trust, 1983. Print.
- Cohen , Signe. qz.com/india/1585631/the-ancient-connections-between-atheism-buddhism-and-hinduism. 3 April 2019. 18 April 2023.
- en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Prophets_and_messengers_in_Islam. n.d. 14 April 2024.
- Gambhirananada, Swami. "Mundaka Upanishad." Kolkata: Advaita

- Ashrama, 2017. II.ii.3-4. Print.
- Gambhirananda, S. *Svetasvatara Upanishad*. Kolkata: Advaita Ashrama, 2016.
- Gambhirananda, Swami. *Aitareya Upanisad*. Kolkata: Advaita Ashrama, 2019.
- . *Kena Upanishad*. Trans. Gambhirananda. 9th. Mayavati: Advaita Ashrama, 2017. Print.
- Gambhirananda, Swami. “Mandukya Upanisad.” Kolkata: Advaita Ashrama, 2016. Print.
- Gambhirananda, Swami. “Mandukya Upanishad.” Kolkata: Advaita Ashrama Publication Department, 2016. 1.2. Print.
- George, Alex Andrews. www.clearias.com/indian-philosophy-schools/. 23 June 2021. 16 March 2023.
- hinduism.stackexchange.com/questions/18987/avataravaada-and-vedanta-are-there-any-contradiction? 6 July 2017. 18 November 2022.
- Jayaram V. www.hinduwebsite.com/symbolism/ramayana.asp. n.d. 12 March 2023.
- Klostermaier, Klaus. *Mokṣa and Critical Theory, Philosophy East and West*, Vols. 35, No.1. 1985 January. <Klaus Klostermaier, Mokṣa and Critical Theory, Philosophy East and West, Vol. 35, No. 1 (Jan., 1985), pp. 61-71>. legacy.quran.com/16/36. n.d. 12 April 2024.
- Madhavananda, Swami. *Vivekachudamani Of Sankaracharya(335)*. Almora: Advaita Ashrama, 1944.
- Parthasarathy, Swami. www.exoticindiaart.com/book/details/symbolism-of-hindu-gods-and-rituals-nam691/. 2009. November 18 2022.
- Rama Devi, S. hdl.handle.net/10603/385180-*The concept of dharma with reference to Ramayana a critical analysis*. 2015. 25 November 2022.
- Ranganadanandaswamikal. *Srimad Bhagavad Gita* . Thrissur: Sri Ramakrishna Math., 1970.
- Sai. hinduism.stackexchange.com/questions/14114/how-does-adishankaracharya-advaita-explain-concept-of-avatar. 18 July 2016. 28 January 2023.
- Sai Lakshmi, Desaraju Sri. www.vedamu.org/Veda/Ramayana_VOLUME II with index.pdf-*Ramayana: A Divine Drama*. 7 December 2012. 24 March 2022.
- Samples, Kenneth. reasons.org/explore/blogs/reflections/how-christ-s-incarnation-differs-from-the-hindu-idea-of-avatar. 22 December 2015. 14 May 2023.
- Sarma, Vidwan Ranganatha. preksha.in/article/nature-moksha-and-srimad-bhagavatam (page1). 6 August 2021. 14 November 2022.
- shankaracharya.org/advaita_vedanta.php/*The Advaita Philosophy Of Sri Sankara*. n.d. 17 May 2024. </advaita_vedanta.php>.
- Sharma, Gaurav. www.thehindu.com/features/friday-review/theatre/ramayan-as-retold-in-asia/article2909774.ece. 19 February 2012. 19

March 2023.

- Sivanandaonline.org.Dctrine of Avtarhood.* n.d. 14 May 2023.
sivanandaonline.org/Brahma Sutras. 2020. 21 June 2023.
 Srinivasan, Vijay. *ramanuja.org/sri/BhaktiListArchives/Article?p=jan96%2F0025.html.* 4th January 1996. 25 November 2022.
 Thibaut, George. *www.wisdomlib.org/hinduism/book/brahma-sutras-thibaut/d/doc64014.html.* 21 February 2015. 25 November 2022.
 Turlapati, Lakshman Prudhvi Simha. *www.quora.com/Why-did-Lord-Vishnu-take-9-avatars-when-he-could-have-done-the-same-thing-in-his-real-form.* 3 December 2017. 13 May 2024.
 V, Jayaram. *The Meaning and Concept of Incarnation in Hinduism.* *www.hinduwebsite.com/incarnation.asp.* n.d. 22 May 2023.
 Valea, Ernest. *www.comparativereligion.com/avatars.html.* n.d. 19 May 2023.
 Wrenn, Chase B. *iep.utm.edu/, Naturalistic Epistemology.* 5 April 2024. 13 June 2024.
 Yati, Nitya Chaitanya. “Brihadaranyaka Upanishad (Vol.II Muni Kaandam).” Vol. 2. Kottayam: D.C.Books, 1995. 3 vols. 4.3.6-7. Print.
yogananda.com.au/upa/Upanishads03.html. n.d. 27 May 2023.
yogapedia.com/definition/5395/avatar. 21 December 2023. 20 February 2024.

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XVI. Book I-IV

January - December 2024

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation,